

INVESTIGATION OF THICKNESS EFFECTS ON SHEAR CHARACTERISATION OF COMPOSITES MATERIALS FOR AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

This paper reviews the state of the art in composite shear testing. There is increasing application of composites in significant structural components in aircraft. With the application of advanced composites in critical locations of aircraft wings, the thickness effects of composite joints or structures should be considered. The main focus of this research is the effect of thickness and out-of-plane properties on shear strength. Several different approaches are proposed to measure and estimate shear strength with both experimental procedures and Finite Element Modelling. In this paper, both Iosipescu and modified short-beam bending tests are proposed to measure the out-plane properties of thick laminates employing both 3D full-field Digital Imaging Correlation (DIC) and strain gauges to capture the strain distribution. The out-of-plane property G_{23} of thick laminates (4-20 mm) has been measured on unidirectional CFRP laminates. This research is supported by the AVIC First Aircraft Institute (FAI) and Beijing Aeronautical Manufacturing Technology Research Institute (BAMTRI) at the AVIC Centre of Structural Design and Manufacture at Imperial College London.

1 INTRODUCTION

As the amount percentage of composite materials utilization in aircraft structure is increasing rapidly resulted from the development of composite materials and the higher requirement of aircraft structures, the composite materials is beginning to serve in the critical heavy-loading carrying components. Till now, the influences of out-plane properties of composites was always treated as minor in structural analysis and material properties evaluation during design; this is because most of the evaluation methods come from the experience and work that composite materials are either applied in secondary components and are treated as thin enough to be dominated by in-plane properties. [1]

The lacking of evaluation of thick Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) composite laminates used in critical loading area in aircraft will cause problems when designing the structures in high safety and reliability standards. This report will emphasize the significance of evaluating thickness effect of CFRP composite laminates and propose an approach to solve this challenge. [2]

The purpose of this research is to improve the safety and reliable factor when designing thick CFRP laminates dominated joint and wing structure from both the engineering structural aspect and materials perspective. [3, 4]

To accomplish this, the first things to do are measuring out-plane mechanical properties of thick CFRP laminates using modified standard ASTM testing methods. After all the essential material properties data are obtained, the next step is to apply these property data into Finite Element Analysis to identify and match different failure criterions arisen by WWFE. Then, the combination of complicated loading conditions and complex structures are needed to be considered to comprehensively evaluate all the engineering designing factors as a whole to improve the designing. [5]

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 MATERIAL

The Carbon fibre reinforced composite laminates were provided by AVIC and the V-notched samples were cut by Water jet cutter via Control Water jet Cutter company in England, the sample dimension is shown in Figure 1, which is determined by ASTM standard D5379. The sheet laminate material was cut in two different orientations to measure G13 and G23 respectively as shown in Figure 1. For measuring G13 the 0° fibre direction is along the longitude orientation of sample, for G23 the 0° fibre direction is along the out-plane direction.

E_1 /MPa	E_2 /MPa	ν_{12}	G_{12} /MPa	X_t /MPa	X_c /MPa	Y_t /MPa	Y_c /MPa	S /MPa
135000	8800	0.33	4470	1548	1226	55.5	218	89.9

Table 1. Material properties of CFRP

Figure 1. Sample geometry

The finished samples were sprayed with white and black speckle which will provide strain information for Digital Imaging Correlation use, the finished sample and speckled sample were shown in Figure 1.

2.2 IOSIPESCU SHEAR TEST

Figure 2. Iosipescu testing rig

The Figure 2 shows a typical Iosipescu testing rig, the loading cells will apply compressive load on the Bearing Posts and this will generate pure shear stress in the middle area of a V-notched CFRP sample. The Figure 2 shows the force and shear diagram for this test. What we are trying to do is to obtain the pure and uniform shear stress state in the middle area to measure the shear stiffness and strength in this testing method. Concerning the strain data, the DIC technique is chosen to measure the full-field shear strain; the shear strain will be necessary for both experimental measurements and parameter identification inversion and future work.

2.3 3-D DIC SET UP

Figure 3. Experiment and DIC set up

Digital Imaging Correlation Technique can capture the surface imaging information of sample along the deformation and transfers the imaging data into strain data through specific algorithm. DIC is an optics and computer based technique, the outstanding features of it include it can capture the real-time and true whole-field strain without destructive effects. For most DIC software, there are importing interface for CAD and FE simulation. The 3D DIC is also ideal for non-flat sample or out-plane deformation occurrence.

The samples were prepared with stochastic speckle patterns with black and white paints for DIC. The shear tests were performed on a hydraulic Instron Machine as shown in Figure 3. The shear rigs with samples are located between the loading cells, 2- camera DIC system was facilitated to capture the strain distribution during test, the setup of DIC system and shear testing is shown in Figure 3. The calibration and photo taking process of DIC is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Calibration process

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 G13

Figure 5. G13 DIC result

From the G13 DIC result, we can see the stress concentration and delamination between layers through thickness. As the loading increasing, the first crack happen at the top and bottom V-notch edge and the crack propagate between layers. Then the stress concentrate at the V-notch area and generate the other crack along the middle area. As long as the load increase, the crack spread into the centre part of the sample until the whole sample breaks. Although the shear happen in the middle part, but at the corner of the sample we can still see two stress concentrate at top and bottom contact area. This would affect the result.

Figure 6. G13 Strain and stress curve

Above is the strain and stress curve. As we can see in the curve, at the first part, the curve is linear increasing until the two initial crack happen, this part always used for structure design as the safety issue. Then the curve turns in to the non-linear part and continue for a long stage until more crack happen in the middle part of the sample.

3.2 G23

Figure 7. G23 DIC result

From the figure 7, we can see the G23 result from DIC, the stress concentrate at the top and bottom side contact part, and then the part under V-notch area. The G23 test is all about the resin. The shear strain is only near 1%, so the top and bottom stress concentration would affect the result too much. So the experiment set up for the G23 test is the most important part of the result. As long as the loading increase, the stress concentrate at the centre part of sample. The 3D DIC shows up the good shear angle on the sample as well.

Figure 8. G23 Strain and stress curve

From the strain and stress curve, we can see the curve is linear before the sample breaks. The maximum of the stress is 58MPa at the 0.7% strain for the centre part of the sample. The problem for G23 test is the top and bottom stress concentration. If the strain at the two part higher than the middle so it would break before the middle V-notch point. In order to track the veracity of shear test, the full field 3D DIC is the best way to do so, and make the experiment result much more reliable. This is happen at the other thickness test as well.

4 CONCLUSION

From this series of test, the Iosipescu shear test has been tested in order to get the out of plane shear property of thick laminate CFRP, the test rig has its own limitation and the stress concentration can affect the result especially for G23 test. For the G13 test, it can shows the delamination between layers, and the non-linear stress and strain curve part can be get from the shear test as well.

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